

Economic Anthropology Citational Policy Statement

As we encounter it today, academic writing might be defined by its use of references and citations to make arguments. Academics use citations in their work to trace the genealogy of ideas, acknowledge intellectual labor, explain disciplinary histories, make theoretical interpretations, and to argue for the authority and persuasiveness of arguments. Because citation involves choices about to whom we will grant authority, acts of citation are also inherently political, whether or not we acknowledge those politics. As one might expect the larger inequities of our society have found their way into the construction of academic authority.

Given all of this, a growing body of research across disciplines has demonstrated that:

- Black women scholars are under-cited relative to their representation in anthropology (Smith and Garret Scott, 2021);
- Self-citation rates vary by anthropological subfield and author age (Hutson 2006);
- Non-native English speakers are faced with significant and unacknowledged labor when communicating their research in English (Amano et al. 2023);
- Patterns of citation vary by research field so that bibliometrics measuring “impact” can provide a poor index for the quality of scholarly work (Seglen 1997; Norris and Oppenheim 2010); and
- Author prominence affects peer review outcomes (Huber et al., 2022).

Hutson has also postulated that self-citation practices in archaeology extend to the relational self, with authors more likely to cite members of their social network such as “mentors, collaborators in the field, and fellow students at graduate school” (2006: 14).

These dynamics outlined above underscore that academic citation does not occur in a vacuum; citational practices are affected by many aspects of the identity of both the writer and the authors they cite. Given the dramatically unequal playing field we start with both societally and disciplinarily, the dynamics can serve to amplify distorted citation patterns and repeatedly shut out alternative academic lineages and ways of knowing about the world.

At *Economic Anthropology*, one of our goals is to ensure that authors have the latitude and encouragement to correct these distortions, and cite more widely and more inclusively. Moreover, we highlight our support of authors who are avoiding citing a particular scholar or particular citation chain for ethical reasons. As more instances of harassment, bullying, and abuse come to light within academia it is important to acknowledge the dilemma that many scholars face when bad actors have done intellectual work that is seemingly irreplaceable. We would like all authors to be aware that the editorial board acknowledges the reality of bad actors within the academy and is supportive of flexible strategies for addressing citational politics.

Economic Anthropology is an academic journal, rather than a newspaper. As such, we are not a venue for primary accusation, fact-finding, or punitive action. We are, however, attempting to explicitly address the ethical dilemmas intrinsic to citational politics through a few structural, policy mechanisms.

First, we encourage authors to cite widely and make use of alternative chains of authority and knowledge networks if it is appropriate to their scholarship. Authors might consider, too, making use of a cover letter

or a note to the editor to explain what they're up to and help ensure they get a fair review. Often, we're not aware of what we're not aware of, and collaboration with authors can help remedy this;

Second, our editorial process deliberately involves multiple members of the editorial board and acknowledges different ways of justifying and explaining the generation of knowledge;

Third, we have a process for receiving and reviewing (and appealing!) complaints if we mess up; and

Fourth and finally, we are developing a *New Directions* forum to act as an incubator for alternative citation chains. To date, deliberate work to redirect citation chains has been largely conducted by early career scholars on an ad hoc basis in non-peer reviewed venues. The work is crucial for the field, but will not be legible to the hiring committees that will allow these ECRs to remain in the discipline. The purpose of *New Directions*, then, is twofold. First, it will provide a peer-reviewed forum to allow authors to redirect citations from bad actors, and receive academic "credit" for doing this important work. Second, it will allow scholars to highlight new, underacknowledged, or unrecognized scholarship on important topics in economic anthropology.

We plan on launching *New Directions* as a special section of our annual open issue, edited by Jess Beck an Editor on the Archaeology and Biological Anthropology Desks, and a member of the Peer Review Committee. We will send out a call in the Spring of 2024 with more detailed information.

In sum, the goal at *Economic Anthropology* is to seek out affirmative strategies for widening the breadth of knowledge we draw upon in our scholarship.

References

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